

Estimated cases of infections in Brazil using the SEIRS model

Figure 1: Brazil

North region

Figure 2 – Acre

Figure 3 – Amapá

Figure 4 – Amazonas

Figure 5 – Pará

Figure 6 – Rondônia

Figure 7 – Roraima

Figure 8 – Tocantins

Northeast Region

Figure 9 – Alagoas

Figure 10 – Bahia

Figure 11 – Ceará

Figure 12 – Maranhão

Figure 13 – Paraíba

Figure 14 – Pernambuco

Figure 15 – Piauí

Figure 16 – Rio Grande do Norte

Figure 17 – Sergipe

Midwest region

Figure 18 – Distrito Federal

Figure 19 – Goiás

Figure 20 – Mato Grosso

Figure 21 – Mato Grosso do Sul

Southeast region

Figure 22 – Espírito Santo

Figure 23 – Minas Gerais

Figure 24 – Rio de Janeiro

Figure 25 – São Paulo

South region

Figure 26 – Paraná

Figure 27 – Rio Grande do Sul

Figure 28 – Santa Catarina

SEIRS model estimates for Scenario 1

Figure 29 – Brazil

North region

Figure 30 – Acre

Figure 31 – Amapá

Figure 32 – Amazonas

Figure 33 – Pará

Figure 34 – Rondônia

Figure 35 – Roraima

Figure 36 – Tocantins

Northeast Region

Figure 37 – Alagoas

Figure 38 – Bahia

Figure 39 – Ceará

Figure 40 – Maranhão

Figure 41 – Paraíba

Figure 42 – Pernambuco

Figure 43 – Piauí

Figure 44 – Rio Grande do Norte

Figure 45 – Sergipe

Midwest region

Figure 46 – Distrito Federal

Figure 47 – Goiás

Figure 48 – Mato Grosso

Figure 49 – Mato Grosso do Sul

Southeast region

Figure 50 – Espírito Santo

Figure 51 – Minas Gerais

Figure 52 – Rio de Janeiro

Figure 53 – São Paulo

South region

Figure 54 – Paraná

Figure 55 – Rio Grande do Sul

Figure 56 – Santa Catarina

SEIRS model estimates for Scenario 2

Figure 57 – Brazil

North region

Figure 58 – Acre

Figure 59- Amapá

Figure 60 – Amazonas

Figure 61 – Pará

Figure 62 – Rondônia

Figure 63 – Roraima

Figure 64– Tocantins

Northeast Region

Figure 65– Alagoas

Figure 66– Bahia

Figure 67– Ceará

Figure 68– Maranhão

Figure 69– Paraíba

Figure 70– Pernambuco

Figure 71– Piauí

Figure 72– Rio Grande do Norte

Figure 73– Sergipe

Midwest region

Figure 74– Distrito Federal

Figure 75– Goiás

Figure 76– Mato Grosso

Figure 77– Mato Grosso do Sul

Southeast region

Figure 78– Espírito Santo

Figure 79– Minas Gerais

Figure 80– Rio de Janeiro

Figure 81– São Paulo

South region

Figure 82– Paraná

Figure 83– Rio Grande do Sul

Figure 84– Santa Catarina

SEIRS model estimates for Scenario 3

Figure 85- Brazil

North region

Figure 86- Acre

Figure 87- Amapá

Figure 88- Amazonas

Figure 89- Pará

Figure 90- Rondônia

Figure 91- Roraima

Figure 92- Tocantins

Northeast Region

Figure 93- Alagoas

Figure 94- Bahia

Figure 95- Ceará

Figure 96- Maranhão

Figure 97- Paraíba

Figure 98- Pernambuco

Figure 99- Piauí

Figure 100- Rio Grande do Norte

Figure 101- Sergipe

Midwest region

Figure 102- Distrito Federal

Figure 103- Goiás

Figure 104- Mato Grosso

Figure 105- Mato Grosso do Sul

Southeast region

Figure 106- Espírito Santo

Figure 107- Minas Gerais

Figure 108- Rio de Janeiro

Figure 109- São Paulo

South region

Figure 110- Paraná

Figure 111- Rio Grande do Sul

Figure 112- Santa Catarina

Estimates of deaths from the SEIRS model for Scenario 1

Figure 113- Brazil

North region

Figure 114- Acre

Figure 115- Amapá

Figure 116- Amazonas

Figure 117- Pará

Figure 118- Rondônia

Figure 119- Roraima

Figure 120- Tocantins

Northeast Region

Figure 121- Alagoas

Figure 122- Bahia

Figure 123- Ceará

Figure 124- Maranhão

Figure 125- Paraíba

Figure 126- Pernambuco

Figure 127- Piauí

Figure 128- Rio Grande do Norte

Figure 129- Sergipe

Midwest region

Figure 130- Distrito Federal

Figure 131- Goiás

Figure 132- Mato Grosso

Figure 133- Mato Grosso do Sul

Southeast region

Figure 134- Espírito Santo

Figure 135- Minas Gerais

Figure 136- Rio de Janeiro

Figure 137- São Paulo

South region

Figure 138- Paraná

Figure 139- Rio Grande do Sul

Figure 140- Santa Catarina

Estimates of deaths from the SEIRS model for Scenario 2

Figure 141- Brazil

North region

Figure 142- Acre

Figure 143- Amapá

Figure 144- Amazonas

Figure 145- Pará

Figure 146- Rondônia

Figure 147- Roraima

Figure 148- Tocantins

Northeast Region

Figure 149- Alagoas

Figure 150- Bahia

Figure 151- Ceará

Figure 152- Maranhão

Figure 153- Paraíba

Figure 154- Pernambuco

Figure 155- Piauí

Figure 156- Rio Grande do Norte

Figure 157- Sergipe

Midwest region

Figure 158- Distrito Federal

Figure 159- Goiás

Figure 160- Mato Grosso

Figure 161- Mato Grosso do Sul

Southeast region

Figure 162- Espírito Santo

Figure 163- Minas Gerais

Figure 164- Rio de Janeiro

Figure 165- São Paulo

South region

Figure 166- Paraná

Figure 167- Rio Grande do Sul

Figure 168- Santa Catarina

Estimates of deaths from the SEIRS model for Scenario 3

Figure 169- Brazil

North region

Figure 170- Acre

Figure 171- Amapá

Figure 172- Amazonas

Figure 173- Pará

Figure 174- Rondônia

Figure 175- Roraima

Figure 176- Tocantins

Northeast Region

Figure 177- Alagoas

Figure 178- Bahia

Figure 179- Ceará

Figure 180- Maranhão

Figure 181- Paraíba

Figure 182- Pernambuco

Figure 183- Piauí

Figure 184- Rio Grande do Norte

Figure 185- Sergipe

Midwest region

Figure 186- Distrito Federal

Figure 187- Goiás

Figure 188- Mato Grosso

Figure 189- Mato Grosso do Sul

Southeast region

Figure 190- Espírito Santo

Figure 191- Minas Gerais

Figure 192- Rio de Janeiro

Figure 193- São Paulo

South region

Figure 194- Paraná

Figure 195- Rio Grande do Sul

Figure 196- Santa Catarina